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D4.1 Policies Explainability and Interpretation Framework V1

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Abbreviations

AWS	Amazon Web Services
BDV	Big Data Value
BDVA	Big Data Value Association
CRISP-DM	Cross-Industry Standard Process for Data Mining
CSV	Comma Separated Values
CSV	Comma Separated Values
DB	DataBase
DL	Deep Learning
EC	European Commission
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ETL	Extract, Transform, and Load
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
H2020	Horizon 2020 Program of the European Commission
HPC	Cloud and High Performance Computing
IaaS	Infrastructure-as-a-Service
IdP	Identity Provider
IPC	Independent Component Analysis
KDD	Knowledge Discovery in Databases
ML	Machine Learning
NER	Named-Entity Recognition
NLP	Natural Language Processing
OIDC	OpenID Connect
PaaS	Platform-as-a-Service
PCA	Principal Component Analysis
RA	Reference Architecture
SHAP	SHapley Additive exPlanations
SSH	Secure Shell Protocol
TOSCA	Topology and Orchestration Specification for Cloud Applications

VM	Virtual Machine
VO	Virtual Organisation
VPME	Virtualized Policy Management Environment
WP	Work Package
XAI	eXplainable AI
XML	eXtensible Markup Language

Executive summary

AI4PublicPolicy is a joint effort of policy makers and Cloud/AI experts to unveil AI's potential for automated, transparent and citizen-centric development of public policies. To this end, the project will deliver, validate, demonstrate and promote a novel Open Cloud platform (i.e., AI4PublicPolicy platform) for automated, scalable, transparent and citizen-centric policy management based on unique AI technologies.

AI4PublicPolicy will provide public authorities, public administrators and other policy making stakeholders with a complete environment for AI-based policy making. Policy makers will be able to design, develop, deploy, validate and fine-tune data-driven, evidence-based policies from a single-entry point.

The AI4PublicPolicy Policy Making Process leverages on the CRISP-DM methodology to address the following objectives:

- Provide a data-driven, AI-based and evidence-based approach
- Promote and facilitate the collaboration between Policy Makers and AI Experts
- Involve citizens and other stakeholders in the Policy evaluation and optimization
- Boost the acceptance of the policies presenting and explaining the Policy development outcomes
- Reuse and share the Policy development models and Datasets across different domains and countries

The AI4PublicPolicy Reference Architecture takes into account and addresses the following concerns of the BDV Reference Model:

- Data Analytics.
- Data Protection
- Data Processing Architectures
- Data management
- Cloud and High-Performance Computing
- Data sharing platforms
- Cybersecurity and Trust

The components of the AI4PublicPolicy RA are divided into three main subsystems or pillars:

- Reusable and Interoperable Dataset
 - Dataset Collection and Management
 - Semantic Interoperability
 - Cross Country Interoperability
 - Datasets and Policies Catalogue
- Policy Transparency and Trust
 - Explainable AI (XAI)
 - Policy Explainability and Interpretation

- AI Security
- AutoML
- Policy Extraction and Evaluation
 - Text and Sentiment Analysis
 - Policy Extraction
 - Policy Evaluation and Optimization
 - VPME

The AI4PublicPolicy platform is built on top of the multi-layered EOSC Compute Platform. Its main layers are:

- The **Federated Resource Providers** layer
- The **Compute and Data Federation** layer
- The **Platforms** layer
- The vertical **Service Management Tools** layer

The components and the whole Reference Architecture have been validated towards both the Conceptual Model, describing how the components interact to fulfil the AI-based Policy Making Process in the main high-level scenarios, and the Pilots user stories reported in deliverable D2.1, mapping the components to the needs of each user story.

1 Introduction

1.1 The AI4PublicPolicy Project

The AI4PublicPolicy platform will be an Open Virtualized Policy Management Environment (VPME) that will provide fully-fledged policy development/management functionalities based on AI technologies such as Machine Learning (ML), Deep Learning (DL), NLP and chatbots, while leveraging citizens' participation and feedback. It will support the entire policy development lifecycle, based on technologies for the extraction, simulation, evaluation and optimization of interoperable and reusable public policies, with emphasis on citizen-centric policies development and optimization through the realisation of citizen-oriented feedback loops. AI4PublicPolicy will complement public policy development functionalities with the ever-important process reengineering and organisation transformation activities towards ensuring the effective transition from legacy policy development models to emerging AI-based policy making.

The AI4PublicPolicy VPME will be integrated with EOSC with a dual objective. First to facilitate access to the Cloud and HPC resources of EOSC/EGI that are required to enable the project's AI tools, second to boost the sustainability and wider use of the project's developments. AI4PublicPolicy's business plan for sustaining, expanding and commercialising the AI tools and the VPME is based on the development of a community of interested and engaged stakeholders (i.e., public authorities and other policy makers) around the project's platform.

Figure 1. AI4PublicPolicy methodological approach

1.2 Description of WP4

Work Package 4 (WP4) is the main AI engine of the AI4PublicPolicy project. The key goal of this WP is to support public administrators through tools to automate the use of AI models, complemented with techniques that both secure and provide explanations on the decisions made by the AI

algorithms. It is composed of many tasks which essentially build up the main AI components. WP4 main tasks are the explainable AI (XAI) for the interpretation of policies (T4.1), the main tools / AI algorithms which consist of the policy explainability and interpretation (T4.2), the secure operation of the AI algorithms and tools (T4.3), the secure and transparent sharing of policy data (T4.4) and the automatic ML (AutoML) (T4.5).

The main objectives of WP4 are to:

- Design and implement explainable AI (XAI) techniques to increase the transparency and safety of AI systems in policy making.
- Deliver security solutions to protect against evasion and poisoning attacks that would affect the outcomes of the AI algorithms.
- Facilitate secure and transparent sharing of policy datasets to foster policy sharing between different stakeholders.
- Support policy makers in the use of AI tools through technologies that automate the overall AI-related process.

1.3 Objective of the Deliverable

WP3, WP4 and WP5 are the core technical work packages of the project, which focus on three independent and complementary streams of technological work driven by the technical specifications and the AI4PublicPolicy platform architecture provided by WP2. WP4 is the connection between WP3, WP5 and WP6. The tools which will be created will be the steppingstone for these other packages. Furthermore, WP4 along with WP5 will be the main work packages that will realize the AI models and tools which will digitalise the policy-making activities within the project.

1.4 Structure of the Deliverable

This deliverable addresses the first implementation of the Policies and Explainability and Interpretation Framework V1. The tools and algorithms implemented in the first implementation phase will be described and demonstrated.

1.5 Structure of the document

This document is comprised of the following chapters:

- The **first chapter** of the document presents an introduction to the project and the document.
- The **second chapter** of the document presents the Background and state of the art.
- The **third chapter** of the document presents the solution design.
- The **fourth chapter** of the document presents the implementation.
- The **fifth chapter** of the document presents the conclusions and future works.

2 Background and State of the art

Artificial Intelligence is revolutionizing a plethora of fields nowadays from automating simple everyday tasks to digitizing industries such as shipping and healthcare. The benefits that come with its use are the reason that most business sectors are incorporating it. The public sector is no exception and has already started to harvest the fruits of artificial intelligence (AI) by transforming the cities into smart ones and through the services it creates for citizens. Machine learning is the main subfield of artificial intelligence used for creating models for forecasting. Machine learning is able to “learn” based on historical data or even use real-time data to enhance performance and make real-time decisions. The vast amounts of data in the possession of public authorities which are collected from the various sensors are being used in order to create meaningful and accurate statistical machine learning models. Machine learning incorporates a variety of models, from simpler statistical models such as KNN and Logistic regression to very complex ones such as Artificial neural networks. Artificial neural networks, although being very powerful and can produce incredible and accurate results, are not interpretable and the user cannot explain their results and which features from the dataset had the most influence on the model predictions. This problem nowadays is tried to be solved through the development of explainable AI (XAI) tools.

2.1 Machine Learning for Policy Making

Policy making is an excellent field for machine learning to unfold its potential and reshape how policies are made. Analysis and visualization of the vast amounts of data which exist in databases can produce invaluable insights for the policy makers and aid them in their process to shape better policies. Moreover, artificial intelligence and specifically machine learning can leverage the different sources of datasets efficiently and cost effectively to produce predictions which will then act as an assistant to policy makers towards taking the right decisions. The tools created with the aid of machine learning can help to revolutionize many areas in which policy making takes place such as crime, health, environment and education. On the other hand, although the advancements in machine learning can transform policy making fundamentally, the lack of interpretable results from the AI models can be a major obstruction for policy makers to adopt such techniques and tools. However, explainable AI (XAI) is trying to solve this issue and attempts to explain the artificial neural networks which mainly are “black boxes” [14]. By this, policy making will be hugely assisted with the use of ML techniques and algorithms. The results will then be interpreted with the right tools which in their turn will be able to immensely support the policy making process and eventually lead to better policies for the citizens and society.

2.2 Explainable AI (XAI)

DARPA defined explainable AI (XAI) as AI systems that can explain their rationale to a human user, characterize their strengths and weaknesses, and convey an understanding of how they will behave in the future [1]. The objective is to create effective explanations that enable end users to understand and trust AI systems. The use of machine learning algorithms trained with large amounts of data is common nowadays, and many times used in critical systems such as health and self-driving cars. The need to understand the decisions made by such algorithms is recognized by the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). The GDPR introduced a right of explanation for all individuals to obtain meaningful explanations of the logic involved when automated decision making takes place. One of the risks of AI is the risk of inadvertently making wrong decisions, learned from artifacts or spurious correlations in the training data.

Article [3] proposes a pipeline for building machine learning models with explanations based on the proposal in [4] which includes an *understanding phase* and an *explaining phase* (Figure 1). The *understanding phase* happens during model training. The goal is to improve the model so that it works properly when the model is deployed. The explanations in this phase refer to interpreting the important features, learnt patterns and ensuring the data bias is not propagated to the model. XAI helps in debugging the model, detecting bias, and building a robust model. The *explaining phase* happens when the trained model is deployed and being used. The goal is to understand how predictions are made by the model. This will help in better decision making and justifiability. Explainability is associated with the notion of explanation as an interface between humans and a decision maker that is, at the same time, both an accurate proxy of the decision maker and comprehensible to humans [2].

Figure 2. ML pipeline with explanations

XAI methods are divided in three categories based on the explanation level, implementation level and model dependency [ComputerGraphicsSurvey]. The *explanation level* indicates whether the method focuses on the model itself and its working and decision making (*global explanations*). Global explanations analyze the decision-making process, providing an overall analysis of the model and its behaviour. Examples are feature importance and partial dependence plots. The explanation may refer to the analysis of a given prediction and the decisions made by the model (*local explanations*), for instance LIME (Local Interpretable Model-Agnostic Explanations), SHAP (Shapley Additive Explanations) provide local explanations for a given dataset. Local explanations provide details on the prediction made.

The implementation model explanations are either *intrinsic* (provided by the model, *white-box model*) on how the model has made a prediction through the model parameters or rules (e.g., Bayesian Rule Lists) or *post-hoc* explanations, which describe the decision-making process of black-box models (e.g., LIME and saliency maps). White-box models are in general simple and self-explanatory, for instance a linear model is transparent and visualized with a line chart. Neural networks are an example of black-box models whose internals are not easy to understand and it is not clear how a feature impacts a decision.

Model dependency is either model-specific or *model-agnostic* that is, the explanations are only valid for a model (specific algorithm) or are valid for any model (any machine learning model). Anchors, LIME and SHAP are examples of the latter.

Data Explanation

Several types of data are used by machine learning techniques, being the most common type of data organized in tables. Other common type of data are images and text [2]. These types of data need to be transformed into arrays to be processed. Data visualization and exploratory analysis is considered the first step of explainability [3]. Dimensionality reduction techniques such as Principal Component Analysis (PCA), Independent Component Analysis (IPC), correlation matrix and autoencoders are used for the visualization and interpretation of data.

White-box Models

Linear models (e.g., linear regression) are easy to explain since they correspond to an equation.

Decision trees are a tree structure where an internal node represents feature (or attribute), the branch represents a decision rule, and each leaf node represents the outcome.

Generalized Additive Models are a generalized linear model in which the linear response variable depends linearly on unknown smooth functions of some predictor variables.

Most of the software packages for creating these models (e.g., Keras, Sklearn) provide a visualization of the model and the decisions.

Black-box Models

Tree ensembles is a learning technique that combines several decision trees to make an optimal decision.

Support vector machines are a classification method for N-dimensional data. It creates a hyperplane that maximizes the distance between data points in different classes.

Neural networks were inspired by biological neural networks where neurons are connected and when a neuron receives a signal, it processes and transmits the result to its downstream connected neurons. They may have several hidden layers that make it difficult to understand how a prediction is made for a given input. *Deep neural networks* have non-linear relationships in the hidden layers. Convolutional neural networks and Recurrent Neural networks are deep neural networks used for image processing and language processing, respectively.

There are several techniques for interpreting black-box models [2]:

- *Decision tree* is one of the most understandable models, primarily for global, but also for local explanations.
- *Decision Rules* provide textual information in the form of if-then rules. They are also one of the most understandable techniques.

- *Saliency Mask* is a visual representation of the features' performance that highlights the relevant aspects of the item analyzed. They are generally used to explain deep neural networks.
- *Partial Dependence Plot* provides local information for understanding the relationship between the outcome of a black-box model and the input in a reduced feature space.
- *Prototype Selection*. It returns, together with the outcome, an example very similar to the classified record. A prototype is an object that is representative of a set of similar instances and is part of the observed points, or it is an artifact summarizing a subset of them with similar characteristics.
- *Activation Maximization*. Observing which are the fundamental neurons activated with respect to particular input records, i.e., to look for input patterns that maximize the activation of a certain neuron in a certain layer. Activation maximization can be viewed as the generation of an input image that maximizes the output activation.
- *Sensitivity Analysis*. It helps in identifying how dependent the output is on a particular input. It consists of evaluating the uncertainty in the outcome of a black-box model with respect to different sources of uncertainty in its inputs. It is also known as what-if analysis.

Feature-based techniques describing how input features contribute to the output [3].

- *Features Importance* assigns a weight to the input features (coefficients in a linear model) used by the black-box model. They are the basis of feature reduction.
- *Permutation Importance* defines the importance of a feature by reshuffling the values of the feature and measuring how this affects the performance of a model.
- *Partial Dependence Plot* provides local information for understanding the relationship between the outcome of a black-box model and the input in a reduced feature space. It depicts how a feature affects the prediction.
- *Accumulated Local Effects* depicts the effects on the prediction of each feature isolated from all other features. It circumvents the errors produced by a partial dependence plot when there is a correlation between features.
- *Global surrogate* is an interpretable model (linear, rules or decision tree) developed for approximating black—box models predictions. The surrogate model is trained with independent values of the input data and dependent variables from the prediction.
- *Local Interpretable Model-agnostic Explanations (LIME)* [5] do not depend on the type of data, nor on the type of black-box model, nor on a particular type of comprehensible local predictor or explanation. The explanation is derived locally from the records generated randomly (perturbation) around the record to be explained and weighted according to their proximity to it. A weak point of this approach is the required transformation of any type of data in a binary format. In practice the explanation is only provided through linear models and their features importance, there is a possibility that there is non-linearity in that region.

3 Solution Design

The solution of the policy explainability and interpretation module was designed with in mind to follow the principles of building a proper task-specific AI pipeline so to better interpret and connect the policy definition module with the interpretation of it through the technical module. The pipeline focuses on taking as input the policy's dataset and processing them accordingly in order to better follow the policy definition and the use case scenario it tries to create. Starting from the dataset the in-between modules in the pipeline are the Data Analysis component, the Data Engineering, the AI Policy Models and finally the Explainable AI component. All the components are interconnected and each step of the pipeline produces the input of the next component. In the end the policy defined initially has been translated to a dataset analysis and to a developed model which produces forecasts aligned with the policy definition.

Figure 3. Module Solution Design

3.1 Mapping on the Reference Architecture

The policy explainability and interpretation module has many connections with other modules from the project's architecture as it can be seen in the figure below. Along with the policy extraction module, which are connected, share the task of creating the AI pipelines for the data scientist and eventually for the policy maker. Policy interpretation initiates the interpretation of the policy and its datasets to actual insights and pre-process the relevant data so to be used by the models created in the AI modelling phase, which takes place both in the policy interpretation and policy extraction modules, and finally, the models' results / predictions are re-introduced to the module and are explained through the explainability aspect of the module.

Figure 4. AI4PublicPolicy modules Architecture

3.2 Model Components and Policy Interpretation

The core of the pipeline module lies in the three intermediate components, the data analysis component, the data engineering and the AI modelling. Together they can interpret the policy defined and produce the main results so to be taken into account by the policy maker after being of course input to the explainable AI component.

3.2.1 Data Analysis, Data Engineering and AI Modeling

The data analytics module is responsible for producing the initial analysis on the data, so as to find hidden patterns and insights. Furthermore, it is able to produce visual explanations (barplots, line charts, dynamic plots etc.) by exploiting hidden patterns of data which essentially in the end leads to a better data explanation for the user.

For the visualization part python programming language has been used and a variety of libraries such as Seaborn, Matplotlib and Plotly. These libraries were chosen due to their big range of visualisations they are able to produce, they are open-source libraries and Plotly in particular due to their ability to produce dynamic plots and their ease and problems-free deployment for the VPME platform.

The data engineering component is responsible for the transformation of the dataset in order to get them ready to be used as input to the machine learning model. It incorporates tasks such as just coding certain feature values and normalizing certain values to running correlation tests on the data in order to remove features with correlation and find ways to combine the data in cases the features in the dataset are few, so the model produces eventually high performance in its predictions.

Last but not least the AI modelling component is responsible for developing the machine learning models which will be responsible to produce forecasts based on the initial policy definition. For this reason, many machine learning algorithms were part of the experiments and additional deep learning models such as Multilayer Perceptrons and CNNs and were also used.

3.3 Explainable AI tools for Policy Explainability (XAI)

3.3.1 QARMA

QARMA is a fully parallel/distributed algorithm for extracting all quantitative association rules that hold with a minimum support and confidence on a given training dataset. The algorithm guarantees that all valid (non-redundant) rules of the form

“IF $a_1 \in [l_1, h_1] \dots AND a_n \in [l_n, h_n]$ THEN $T = v$ ” when T is a categorical variable

or of the form

“IF $a_1 \in [l_1, h_1] \dots AND a_n \in [l_n, h_n]$ THEN $T \geq v$ ” and

“IF $a_1 \in [l_1, h_1] \dots AND a_n \in [l_n, h_n]$ THEN $T \leq v$ ” when T is a numerical variable

where a_1, \dots, a_n are numerical attributes (columns) of the dataset and T is the target attribute of the supervised learning problem, are extracted from the dataset.

Once all such rules have been found and collected in a ruleset R , we can provide an explanation for a third-party opaque model M prediction of the value v_M of the unknown target T given values of an instance I for the attributes $a_k \in A$ of the dataset, as follows:

1. we scan the set R and pick the rules $r \in R$ whose antecedent conditions are satisfied by the values of the attributes of the instance I and in addition, the value of the consequent in the rule r is satisfied by the predicted value v_M .
2. If the target variable T is a categorical variable, we return the rule $r \in R$ with the highest confidence; in case of confidence value ties across multiple rules, we return the one that has the highest support; in case there still exist ties, we pick the rule with least number of antecedents (easier to understand).
3. If the target variable T is a continuous variable, we return two rules
 - a. we return the rule of the form “IF $a_1 \in [l_1, h_1] \dots AND a_n \in [l_n, h_n]$ THEN $T \geq v$ ” that provides the closest valid lower-bound in the value of the target variable T , in other words the rule that specifies a value v' for the target variable that is highest among all consequent values v_r of the rules r in R such that $v' = \max(v_r | v_r \leq v_M)$. Ties among rules with value for the consequent equal to v' are resolved by picking the highest confidence rule among them, and any ties still remaining are resolved by considering the highest support rule among them.
 - b. analogous to step (a), but this time we work with the extracted rules of the form “IF $a_1 \in [l_1, h_1] \dots AND a_n \in [l_n, h_n]$ THEN $T \leq v$ ”, and we pick among all rules specifying consequent values higher than v_M .

As long as the resulting rule(set) is not empty, it explains the decision of any opaque classifier/regressor in terms of the specified rule that is found to hold with the specified support and confidence on the training dataset.

3.3.2 QARMA Rest-Service

Given the extracted ruleset (stored in a relational database), the algorithm specified in the previous section (3.3.1) is implemented in a particular REST web service with a base URI endpoint on “/explain”.

The relevant service code is written using the Spring-Boot light-weight framework that greatly simplifies the task of writing web applications with the Spring framework. A `@SpringBootApplication`-annotated class called `QARMARteWsApplication` serves as the main Spring-Boot application class; the class `QARMABasedExplainer` is annotated as `@RestController` and its method `getExplanation(@RequestBody ParkingData pd)` corresponds to the `/explain` URI and is annotated as a `@PostMapping` request. It returns as a result a String representation of the rule(s) that best explain the (third-party) model's prediction; the string also contains the support and confidence values of each rule described in the return string. Clearly, if the returned rules have low confidence values, or even worse, if the return string is empty, this means that the model's prediction has no explanation among the extracted ruleset, and therefore the prediction itself should be further scrutinized if possible. An illustration of the QARMA Rest-Service in action is shown in fig. 1 using the SOAP-UI tool for web service testing for the AI4PP DAEM Parking Use Case.

Figure 5. QARMA RestService API Illustration

3.3.3 DALEX

DALEX (moDel Agnostic Language for Exploration and eXplanation) takes any model and helps to explore and explain its behavior. DALEX package provides operations that help to understand the link between input variables and model output [8]. DALEX is an R package that creates a layer of abstraction around models to provide a standardized uniform interface for model exploration independent of libraries used to build the model [7]. The model can be developed using Keras, H2O or scikit-learn or other libraries. DALEX library creates a level of abstraction around a model to explore and explain the model (Figure 6). DALEX::explain() function, takes a fitted model and additional metadata to prepare a uniform interface, the explainer, with exposed functions for calculation of predictions, calculation of residuals, operations on the data and the target variable (e.g., feature permutations). All model explainers are model agnostic and can be compared across different models.

Figure 6. DALEX usage

Once the explainer is created, one can use XAI tools available in various packages without worrying about which framework and programming language (R or Python) were used to develop the model. DrWhy.AI provides several packages for visual model exploration around DALEX (Figure 8).

Ingredients [18] package is a collection of tools for assessment of feature importance and feature effects.

Figure 7. DoctorWhy.AI Tools

The *iBreakDown* [19] package is a model agnostic tool for explanation of predictions from black-box models. Break Down Table shows the contributions of every variable to a final prediction. Break Down Plot presents variable contributions in a concise graphical way. SHAP (Shapley Additive Attributions) values are calculated as average from random Break Down profiles. This package works for binary classifiers as well as regression models. *iBreakDown* supports interactions and interactive explainers with D3.js plots. It also provides explanations in natural language *auditor* [20] is a tool for model-agnostic validation. It facilitates assessing and comparing the goodness of fit and

performance of models. Auditor may be used for the analysis of the similarity of residuals and for the identification of outliers and influential observations.

DALEX provides instance level exploration and data set level exploration. Instance level exploration is used to understand how a model produced a given prediction for a particular observation. Given a prediction for an individual we are interested in how much the different variables contributed to that prediction (variable attributions). How this prediction would change if the value of an explanatory variable is changed (what-if analysis). If a given prediction is wrong, what are the reasons for that mistake.

The next fragments of code in Python and charts are taken from [7] using the Titanic dataset. Given a model that predicted the probability of the survival of passenger, Henry, aged 47, traveling in first class, DALEX provides several methods for explaining the result.

Break down for Additive Attributes.

This method explains which variables contributed most to the prediction. The Explainer function takes the model and creates the abstract representation.

```
import dalex as dx

titanic_rf_exp = dx.Explainer(titanic_rf, X, y,
                              label = "Titanic RF Pipeline")
```

Then, the break down method is used to calculate the variables that contributed to the result. This is indicated as a parameter of the predict_parts method of the explainer.

```
bd_henry = titanic_rf_exp.predict_parts(henry,
                                       type = 'break_down')
```

```
bd_henry.plot()
```

the plot method generates a waterfall chart using the Plotly library:

Figure 8. Waterfall chart using the Plotly library

Break down for Interactions

Interaction means that the effect of one variable depends on the values of other variables too.

In this case the parameter for the predict_parts method is break_down_interactions. The interaction_preference indicates the preference for the interactions between the variables.

```
bd_henry = titanic_rf_exp.predict_parts(henry,
```

```
type = 'break_down_interactions',
interaction_preference = 10)
```

The chart presents the result showing the dependency between gender and class, and the fare and embarcation city:

Figure 9. Result showing the dependency between gender and class, and the fare and embarcation location

Shapley Additive Explanations (SHAP) for Average Attributions

With the first method the computed value of the attribution may depend on the order of explanatory covariates that are used in calculations. The previous method identifies the interactions and explicitly presents their contributions to the predictions. The SHAP method for average computations is based on the idea of averaging the value of a variable's attribution over all (or a large number of) possible orderings.

The explainer for the previous model is indicated with the “shap” parameter.

```
bd_henry = titanic_rf_exp.predict_parts(henry, type = 'shap')
```

The chart is produced by the plot function is:

Figure 10. Chart utilising SHAP

Local Interpretable Model-agnostic Explanations (LIME)

Break-down (BD) plots and Shapley values are suitable for models with a small number of explanatory variables. The idea behind LIME is to locally approximate a black-box model by a simpler glass-box model, which is easier to interpret. The data can be an image, text or tabular data. The example uses tabular data.

```
from lime.lime_tabular import LimeTabularExplainer
explainer = LimeTabularExplainer(X,
    feature_names=X.columns,
    class_names=['died', 'survived'],
    discretize_continuous=False,
    verbose=True)
```

The explain_instance() method finds a local approximation with an interpretable linear model

```
lime = explainer.explain_instance(henry, titanic_fr.predict_proba)
lime.show_in_notebook(show_table=True)
```

Producing the following charts:

Figure 11. Charts utilising LIME

Ceteris-paribus Profiles

This method evaluates the effect of a selected explanatory variable in terms of changes in a model’s prediction induced by changes in the variable’s values. This is why the tools are also known as “What-if” model analysis or Individual Conditional Expectations. It is easier to understand how a black-box model works by investigating the influence of explanatory variables separately, changing one at a time.

```
titanic_rf_exp = dx.Explainer(titanic_rf, X, y,
    label = "Titanic RF Pipeline")
```

```
cp_henry = titanic_rf_exp.predict_profile(henry)
cp_henry.plot(variables = ['age', 'fare'])
```

The results are plotted for the variables age and fare:

Figure 12. Plots for Age and Fare

Dashboards are useful for presenting different types of charts and explanations. Arena¹ is a tool for building dashboards for model exploration for Python and R that is compatible with DALEX (Figure 13). Arena will be used to build dashboards in the project.

Figure 13. Arena Dashboard

Neural Networks

*ktrain*² is a lightweight wrapper for the deep learning library TensorFlow Keras to help build, train, and deploy neural networks and other machine learning models. *ktrain* provides the predictor and explain methods to understand how a prediction was made.

```
predictor = ktrain.get_predictor(learner.model, preproc)
```

```
predictor.explain('data/dogscats/valid/cats/cat.5583.jpg')
```

Ktrain explain function displays the image and the area in which the classifier focused to make a decision. For instance, the classifier did not classify this image as having a cat, only dogs because the classifier only focused on the dog as the yellow area highlights (Figure 14).

¹ <https://arena.drwhy.ai/docs/>

² <https://github.com/amaiya/ktrain>

Figure 14. Area the classifier focussed in

4 Implementation

Each pilot has a number of use case scenarios built in order to tackle a variety of problems existing in each city. In addition, to develop a solution for these problems, each pilot has offered a set of datasets. Taking advantage of these datasets, state of art machine learning and deep learning techniques have been developed following the pre-processing of the data in order to produce accurate results and predictions. Alongside the AI models developed a set of problem related custom-made visualizations are also created (wherever possible), so to provide a better understanding of the dataset and to give to the user / policy maker the ability to gain more thorough insights to the problem at hand in order to take the right policy decisions. For the implementation a variety of AI models were used which will be described in each pilot section. The AI models used were initially developed with the use of Jupyter notebooks which were later integrated to the JupyterHub cloud service offered by EGI in order to gain more computational power through their more advanced infrastructure. Furthermore, in the implementation part the architecture which was followed can be seen at Figure 15. The AI pipeline consists of the Data Analysis module which is split into two parts, the data exploration and the data visualization (if possible). Then the data is passed through the pipeline to the data engineering module in which a variety of functions are applied such as the data cleansing, the data normalization and finally the data splitting. Last but not least the AI modelling module is responsible for the model selection, the model training and validation and in the end for the testing evaluation of the overall model performance.

Figure 15. Visual representation of the AI Pipeline

4.1 Athens

The aforementioned AI pipeline has been implemented in two use case scenarios provided by Athens pilot. The first model use case scenario is based in the maintenance policies optimization with the goal to optimally allocate the maintenance and scheduling activities in the city. The second use case scenario is trying to provide citizens with predictions about parking availability in the different areas of the city. In both scenarios all the modules mentioned in the AI pipeline were used and AI pipelines modules were developed with the use of python programming language. More specifically the visualization module was developed with the use of Seaborn, Matplotlib and Plotly libraries [13], [15], [16] and for the development of the Deep Learning part were used Keras and TensorFlow [17] libraries.

4.1.1 Maintenance Policy Optimization

Diving into a more analytical overview for the module of Data Analysis a variation of data visualizations was used, so to better explain the data exploration and provide some insights on the data. The dataset consists of 9 features/variables with the main of them being the creation date, type of issue, address in which the issue occurred, description of the issue, authority service responsible to solve the issue, progress status of the issue, coordinates (longitude and latitude) and completion

date in case the progress status is completed. Based on these variables a variety of visualizations were produced trying to explain the data. In the following figures (Figure 16 and Figure 17) one can observe the issue's progress status in total number so to give a first overview of the municipality's effectiveness to tackle issues. In Figure 18 and Figure 19 the user is able to observe the top 20 incident category types for each progress status. A statistic which can give a simple but effective first explanation of the type of incidents which are effectively tackled, and which are not.

Figure 16. Visual Donut chart of Issues Progress Status

Figure 17. Barplot of Issues Progress Status

Figure 18. Top 20 Issue types (Completed and Pending)

Figure 19. Top 20 Issue types (In Progress and Dismissed)

In the following Figure 20, a dynamic visualization is constructed which lets the user adjust the dates and the authority they want to search for and by this way have a clear overview of the workload and the response rate of an authority to the incidents for a specific range of time. In addition, Figure 21 presents a plot that shows the authorities as bubbles and places them in the plot depending on the amount of time and the number of incidents they have solved. Finally, Figure 22 depicts Athens' map and shows all the incidents along with their progress status label. The visualization also lets the user to focus on whichever labels want by just unselecting the progress status labels in the right panel. Overall, these visualizations help the user to easily gain insights and have the “hidden” information on the dataset translated.

From Date: 10/01/2018

To Date: 04/18/2022

Authority: Διεύθυνση Πρασίνου και Αστική

Authority Services Issues Numbers per Date Period

Figure 20. Progress type - Number of issues plot per Authority Service and Time interval

Authority Services Issues Number Comparison to Average Completion Time

Figure 21. Bubble plot - Average days for issue solution - Number of issues per Authority

Issues Progress Status (60 Days Time)

Figure 22. Map visualization - Issues progress status

The data engineering module is the next step down the pipeline stream and is an essential step in order to continue to the AI modelling module. The data engineering module is correlated with the problem at hand. In order to further assist the maintenance policy, two models were built. The first was a classification problem trying to predict the issue that will arise for a given authority while the second one is a regression problem trying to predict the number of issues that will arise for a specific authority.

4.1.1.1 Issue Prediction

For the issue prediction problem in order to make the problem a little easier and to test its solution, the issues were reduced to the top 20 issues found inside the municipality. Through the date of creation new features were created such as the month and the weekday, so to capture the time information and the coordinates were normalized. In addition, the authority services were encoded via the one hot encoder pre-processing method. Following the AI modelling module, the model finally chosen to be used was a Multi-layer perceptron (MLP) neural network. The selection was based on experimentation with many models, some traditional machine learning models such as KNN and SVMs and some deep neural networks like convolutional neural networks (CNN) [9],[10],[11],[12]. The final choice was based on the performance of the model while trying to keep it as simple as possible and trying to have a “quick” training phase.

Figure 23 shows the MLP’s results on the test dataset. Some classes with a little support are not able to be predicted but as the support grows the precision and recall grows also which results in a higher F1-score. Overall, the model is able to achieve a 74 % of accuracy and a 66 % F1-score of weighted average. These results are proven hopeful, and it is worth to try to enhance the model in the future so to achieve an even better performance.

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
0	0.00	0.00	0.00	2669
1	0.54	0.29	0.37	4960
2	0.00	0.00	0.00	519
3	0.00	0.00	0.00	1114
4	0.99	0.99	0.99	742
5	0.33	0.02	0.03	714
6	0.93	1.00	0.96	12823
7	0.00	0.00	0.00	742
8	0.00	0.00	0.00	1992
9	0.72	1.00	0.84	1606
10	0.00	0.00	0.00	1867
11	0.00	0.00	0.00	538
12	0.00	0.00	0.00	520
13	0.00	0.00	0.00	619
14	0.33	0.78	0.46	858
15	0.76	1.00	0.86	37399
16	0.59	0.84	0.69	7611
17	0.00	0.00	0.00	1162
18	0.00	0.00	0.00	2935
19	0.00	0.00	0.00	676
accuracy			0.74	82066
macro avg	0.26	0.30	0.26	82066
weighted avg	0.61	0.74	0.66	82066

Figure 23. Classification report and model's performance analysis

4.1.1.2 Number of Issues Forecasting

Additional to the first model, a second one was created which aspired to predict the number of issues that can result in a certain month for a certain authority service. As it can be observed at Figure 24, the diagrams show that through the years the number of issues has similar picks or lows depending on the month and the same pattern is also observed for individual authorities. So, based on the above pattern the dataset was pre-processed accordingly. The dataset was arranged based on each authority service, the month, the year and the number of issues for each authority service were summed up. The number of the authority services had to be decreased and this was achieved by merging the sub-authorities to their main authority division. By this we achieved a more concrete and manageable dataset by dropping the total authorities from some thousands to 65. By only using the few features mentioned it achieved a relative absolute error of 35% which can be proved hopeful considering the not so many features used in order to feed our model and the complexity of the problem and of course the variation in the values to be predicted. As it is seen in Figure 25 the actual issues number along with the predicted ones not only our model captures the power of magnitude of the target variable, but it also produces similar predictions. This is hopeful that in the near future it will be possible to be built a more accurate model which can better solve the aforementioned problem.

Figure 24. Number of issues per Month and Year

```

1 : Actual values for prediction: 10 | Model predicted value: 6
2 : Actual values for prediction: 1 | Model predicted value: 2
3 : Actual values for prediction: 20 | Model predicted value: 1
4 : Actual values for prediction: 1 | Model predicted value: 3
5 : Actual values for prediction: 13 | Model predicted value: 6
6 : Actual values for prediction: 1 | Model predicted value: 3
7 : Actual values for prediction: 1419 | Model predicted value: 1587
8 : Actual values for prediction: 548 | Model predicted value: 490
9 : Actual values for prediction: 365 | Model predicted value: 498
10 : Actual values for prediction: 1 | Model predicted value: 2
11 : Actual values for prediction: 3 | Model predicted value: 7
12 : Actual values for prediction: 1 | Model predicted value: 2
13 : Actual values for prediction: 158 | Model predicted value: 193
14 : Actual values for prediction: 29 | Model predicted value: 17
15 : Actual values for prediction: 2 | Model predicted value: 2
16 : Actual values for prediction: 17 | Model predicted value: 18
17 : Actual values for prediction: 32 | Model predicted value: 47
18 : Actual values for prediction: 3 | Model predicted value: 2
19 : Actual values for prediction: 1 | Model predicted value: 1
20 : Actual values for prediction: 1449 | Model predicted value: 2011
    
```

Figure 25. Actual issues number along with the model predicted ones

4.1.2 Predictive Citizen-Centric Parking Policy Development

The second use case scenario developed for Athens municipality is based on the parking policy development. The policy aims at predicting the parking availability in the different city areas/zones so as to make optimal use of on-street parking resources and to achieve high citizen satisfaction. The main dataset consists of various features describing parking space occupancies with some important ones such as the creation date, the parking duration, the coordinates of the parking spaces and the district zones. The data analytics module creates visualizations in order to better present the data and increase the user’s understanding of them. The visualizations created contain a visual representation of Athens zones representations (Figure 26) and in Figure 27 a dynamic plot of visualizing the number of parking spaces for all the dates and times contained in the dataset so the user can understand how the demand changes throughout the time and zones.

Figure 26. Visual representation of Athens zones

Figure 27. Dynamic plot of visualizing the number of parking spaces

The next step in the pipeline is the Data Engineering module and the pre-processing done to the dataset so to gain additional insight on data and eventually get them ready to be used as input to our model. By processing the data, it was observed a pattern through time (Figure 28) for most of parking zones. The pattern is more discernible when we construct the data in 4-hour intervals as shown in Figure 29.

Figure 28. Pattern through time per parking zone

Figure 29. Pattern through time per parking zone (4-hour intervals)

The pattern presented in the figures above was the initiative in order to better prepare the dataset so as to try to predict the parking spaces available for each zone. In order to create our dataset so to predict how many free parking spaces exist each time for each zone, we calculated how many unique parking spaces are filled in the 4-hour interval for each zone and we, furthermore, set each zone’s parking spaces capacity to the maximum free spaces that had in the dates observed in our

initial dataset. Then the calculation of our free parking spaces for each zone is simply calculated through the subtraction of the filled parking spaces from the maximum capacity each zone has. In addition, they also added some more features in order for our model to correlate with the existing ones such as the month, the week, and the date. After the dataset was ready to be “fed” to the models we started building the parking predictions model. Having experimented with many machine learning models we found that the best performance was achieved with a deep neural network and specifically with the use of a multilayer perceptron. Because the problem at hand is a regression problem the model’s performance was measured based on the RAE (relative absolute error) metric which offers protection from the outliers and can be a good indication if our regression model has a good performance. The MLP achieved a RAE of 24.8% or 0.25 which is considered a good value being close to 0.

Furthermore, on top of the model’s prediction Qarma algorithm was introduced through its Rest-Service. The parking model’s predictions were given as input and Qarma was able to produce its explainable set of rules as seen at Figure 30.

```
Qarma response:
[month in (10.0, +Inf)] ^ [hour in (16.0, +Inf)] ^ [max_capacity in (33.0, +Inf)] --> [target > 29.0] (Supp=3.356%/Conf=98.993%) AND [month in [-Inf, 12.0]] --> [target < 31.0] (Supp=81.898%/Conf=81.898%)

Qarma response:
[month in (10.0, +Inf)] ^ [hour in (16.0, +Inf)] ^ [max_capacity in (43.0, +Inf)] --> [target > 38.0] (Supp=3.004%/Conf=99.248%) AND [month in [6.0, 12.0]] ^ [max_capacity in (-Inf, 45.0)] --> [target < 40.0] (Supp=34.725%/Conf=99.414%)

Qarma response:
[hour in (8.0, 12.0)] ^ [parking_zone_cat in (0.0, 2.0)] ^ [max_capacity in (39.0, +Inf)] --> [target > 10.0] (Supp=0.922%/Conf=79.412%) AND [hour in (-Inf, 20.0)] ^ [max_capacity in (-Inf, 41.0)] --> [target < 12.0] (Supp=34.225%/Conf=90.114%)

Qarma response:
[hour in (8.0, 12.0)] ^ [max_capacity in (89.0, +Inf)] --> [target > 25.0] (Supp=1.684%/Conf=72.549%) AND [hour in (-Inf, 20.0)] ^ [max_capacity in (-Inf, 92.0)] --> [target < 27.0] (Supp=69.951%/Conf=96.108%)

Qarma response:
[hour in (8.0, 16.0)] ^ [parking_zone_cat in (11.0, 12.0)] ^ [max_capacity in (62.0, +Inf)] --> [target > 19.0] (Supp=0.307%/Conf=79.412%) AND [hour in (8.0, 20.0)] ^ [max_capacity in (-Inf, 69.0)] --> [target < 21.0] (Supp=39.208%/Conf=97.262%)
```

Figure 30. QARMA algorithm - Set of rules example

4.2 Lisbon

The idea for this pilot is to estimate the number of PVs in Lisbon city by analyzing available satellite images of the city and running an AI algorithm to detect photovoltaic panels (PVs). To achieve this goal, we built an AI pipeline for training the AI model which can be used for detection of solar panels on the given image.

4.2.1 Exploratory Data Analysis

As a starting point for data analysis, we chose to use Californian images because at the moment no labelled images for Lisbon city were available. The goal of this analysis was to understand the California dataset and create an initial AI pipeline and then improve it once Lisbon data is available.

During Exploratory data analysis we tried to answer the following questions:

- What parameters input images should have to achieve an optimal performance and accuracy (resolution, distance to the ground)? As a result of this analysis, we had to add an

additional step in our data preparation process which performs tiling of the images (splitting big resolution images to smaller ones with less resolution);

- What type of data we need to reach the pilot's KPI. For example, we needed to convert label's format from polygons to rectangle as it's a requirement for the AI model we used;
- What is the optimal resolution of images so the detection is accurate, but the performance is still acceptable in training and inference phases;
- Understanding different types of roofs in Lisbon and California datasets and their consequences on the accuracy of the model;

Analyzing those points allowed us to understand how to design the AI pipeline and which requirements we need to specify when asking for a dataset from the pilot.

4.2.2 Data preparation and training

We designed an AI pipeline with the following main steps:

- Data preparation for labels and images;
- Iteratively train the AI model;

Data engineering process consists of the following steps:

- Extract PVs locations from CSV file;
- Normalize labels so that all values fit into [0, 1] interval;
- Convert polygons to rectangles and store them in YOLOv5 format (YOLOv5 library requires rectangles instead of polygons);
- Tiling images: divide big 5000x5000 images to smaller 1000x1000 (better suited for model training);

Training phase includes the following steps:

- Divide the dataset (all images and labels) into train and validation datasets (90% / 10%);
- Run the training algorithm several times (feeding the outcome of the previous iteration to the next one) until there are no noticeable improvements in the accuracy of PVs detection;

4.2.3 Inference phase and model evaluation

The inference phase means running the trained model against an image where PVs need to be detected.

The result of this phase is a list of labels, for every image, with coordinates of rectangles corresponding to detected PVs. For one image this could be visualized as below:

Figure 31. Image with coordinates of rectangles corresponding to detected PVs

Every rectangle corresponds to a detected panel and the number on the right is showing the confidence with which the detection has been done (1.0 - high confidence, 0.0 - low confidence). During the inference phase a threshold can be specified which defines the minimum accuracy needed for the result to be included in the list of detected panels.

Model evaluation

During the training phase there are metrics that we track to estimate the accuracy of the model in the current iteration. These metrics are also used by the YOLOv5 framework to choose an iteration with the best performance and use it as a final model. Also, by tracking these metrics we can see the progress across iterations which helps us to decide if new iterations are needed or not. Those metrics are shown in the figures below:

Figure 32. Progress across iterations

4.3 Burgas

The architecture of the AI pipeline was also implemented in the Burgas pilot use case scenario. Burgas municipality needs to be able to detect leakage in their water pipe infrastructure. In order to be able to do so, an experiment was made in which data were collected from sensors implemented in a small set up as can be seen at Figure 33. A number of scenarios took place during the experiment in which some taps were opened in order to simulate a leakage in the pipe (Figure 33). The sensors used for the experiment were vibration sensors and the dataset provided contained the vibration measurements along with the timestamp at which the measurement was taken. Having the details seen at Figure 34 and the data a dataset constructed which can be observed at Figure 35. From the dataset given at this stage the data analytics module was not able to produce meaningful visualizations so the next AI pipeline module which is the data engineering module is the one to be triggered. From an early visualization of the experimental data, it can be seen that when the tap is

opened or closed the vibration is changed (Figures 36 and 37). The initial experiments with a simple pre-processing of the data did not produce good results so another approach to the dataset was tried. A sliding time-window of 30000 points (corresponding to 5 seconds of wall-clock time) was defined, and 33 points were finally kept as follows: 999 points of every 1000 points were dropped, and was kept only the first one, which resulted in 30 points spread one sixth of a second apart. It also kept the minimum, maximum, and average value of all the 30000 points, for a total of 33 numbers. Therefore, every sliding window resulted in a vector of 33 dimensions. Since a sliding time window was used, the total number of rows in such a dataset would be $N-30000$ where N is the total number of vibration measurements made. Since $N \gg 30000$, the number $N-30000$ is still too big to be managed. For this reason, it was also kept only 1 out of every 100 such vectors that were created, so the dataset is down-sampled by a factor of 100 (keep 1% of all the vectors the above process would normally create). The resulting dataset, though the down-sampling, led to models that obtained 88% overall accuracy and a macro average F1-score of 86% and weighted average F1-score of 88% (Figure 38). Finally, the confusion matrix and the actual numbers and percentages presented at Figure 39 show that the model achieved very good overall performances with the pre-processing done though having data from only a single sensor measuring only water's vibration. Much higher accuracy (approximately 98%) and F-1 score (approximately 97%) are reported on the same dataset when using rule-based methods (instead of neural networks) and cross-validation instead of train-test splitting of the dataset.

Figure 33. Experimental water pipe set up

Scenario	Conditions						Starting Time	
0	All Taps Closed (ATC) 9 min 57 s						12:03	
1	ATC 3 min 2 s	Tap1AB 3 min 5 s	ATC 2 min 18 s				13:00	
1a	ATC 2 min	Tap1SLOpening 31s	Tap1Open 1 min 33 s	ATC 2 min 8 s			13:18	
2	ATC 3 min 16 s	Tap2AB 2 min 46 s	ATC 1 min 46 s				13:25	
2a	ATC 3 min 14 s	Tap2SLOpening 27 s	Tap2Open 1 min 45 s	ATC 2 min 13 s			15:17	
3	ATC 3 min	Tap3AB 2 min 4 s	ATC 2 min 10 s				15:25	
3a	ATC 3 min 11 s	Tap3AB 2 min 6 s	ATC 2 min 11 s				15:33	
4	ATC 3 min 11 s	Tap4AB 2 min 20 s	ATC 2 min 8 s				15:41	
5	ATC 3 min 4 s	Tap2AB 2 min 9 s	Tap2Open + Tap1AB 2 min 11 s	Tap1Open 2 min 13 s	ATC 2 min 5 s		15:49	
6	ATC 3 min 2 s	Tap4AB 2 min 15 s	Tap4Open + Tap1SLOpening 15 s	Tap1Open + Tap4Open 1 min 56 s	Tap1Open 2 min 59 s	ATC 2 min 12 s	16:04	
7	ATC 3 min 30 s	Tap4AB 1 min 16 s	Tap4Open + Tap2AB 1 min 10 s	Tap2Open + Tap4Open + Tap1AB 1 min 1 s	Tap1Open + Tap2Open 1 min 3 s	Tap1Open 1 min 12 s	ATC 1 min 2 s	16:22

Figure 34. Experiment details

	time	modulus	open_tap	scenario
0	0.066571	-9.611669	0	Scenario0
1	0.066720	-6.223372	0	Scenario0
2	0.066870	0.355992	0	Scenario0
3	0.067019	1.031545	0	Scenario0
4	0.067169	-4.878226	0	Scenario0
...
38977979	614.401238	-1.779636	0	Scenario7
38977980	614.401388	-8.641136	0	Scenario7
38977981	614.401537	-0.379339	0	Scenario7
38977982	614.401686	0.443084	0	Scenario7
38977983	614.401836	-7.216029	0	Scenario7

Figure 35. Initial constructed dataset

Figure 36. Opened taps - vibrations visualization

Figure 37. Closed taps - vibrations visualization

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
0	0.92	0.91	0.91	40933
1	0.80	0.81	0.81	18414
accuracy			0.88	59347
macro avg	0.86	0.86	0.86	59347
weighted avg	0.88	0.88	0.88	59347

Figure 38. Classification report - leakage neural network results

```

True Positive number: 14942
True Positive Percent: 25.177346790907713 %

True Negative number: 37251
True Negative Percent: 62.76812644278566 %

False Positive number: 3682
False Positive Percent: 6.204188922776215 %

False Negative number: 3472
False Negative Percent: 5.850337843530422 %
    
```

Confusion Matrix

Figure 39. Confusion Matrix

4.4 Genoa

The use case provided by Genoa's Pilot aims at minimizing the risk of street accidents for vulnerable subjects, such as pedestrians, cyclists and bikers. The objective of the model is to identify dangerous patterns into the city's viability and to minimize the KPIs related to accident's occurrence. The exploratory data analysis was conducted with the use of Pandas, a well-known Python's library and with the use of Pyplot and Folium, two Python's libraries used for charts and maps.

4.4.1 Exploratory Data Analysis

A preliminary analysis was conducted on a dataset containing all the accidents that took place in Genoa during 2021. As mentioned earlier the focus of this pilot is to prevent accidents involving vulnerable subjects so the EDA (Exploratory Data Analysis) was conducted mainly on those kinds of accidents.

The dataset contains 52 features, some regarding the time and place of the accidents, some others the weather's conditions. The street's conditions, along with the number of casualties and injuries and the type of accident were also provided. The first goal of the EDA was to identify potential areas of the city with a particularly high number of accidents; this was made possible by reporting every accident's coordinates on Genoa's map (Figure 40).

Figure 40. Accidents on Genoa's map with the number of peoples involved

From this map it looks like some areas, and more specifically some streets, might be more susceptible to accidents involving vulnerable subjects. After identifying the streets where most of those accidents took place (Figure 41) another map was created (Figure 42). It reports the number of accidents involving vulnerable subjects in each street in 2021 it became more visible that there were areas where those accidents took place more often.

Strada01	NIncidenti
BELVEDERE LORENZO POMODORO	1
VIA MOLASSANA	8
VIA MILANO	3
VIA MERANO	1
VIA MARTIRI DELLA LIBERTA	2
***	***
VIA BRIGNOLE DE FERRARI	2
VIA BRIGATA SALERNO	1
VIA BRIGATA LIGURIA	1
VIA BORZOLI	2
VICO DI SANTA ROSA	1

Figure 41. Number of accidents by street

Figure 42. Number of accidents by street on Genoa's map

Given that Genoa is a touristic destination, the data might hide some kind of seasonality showing an increase of accidents in the months with the highest influx of tourists. Figure 43 shows the number of accidents for each day of the year. It is clear that during the beginning of summer and during the end of the year a higher number of accidents took place.

Figure 43. Number of accidents throughout the year (per day)

In order to have a clearer idea of the aforementioned trend an upsampling was made plotting the number of accidents by month of the year. In Figure # It appears more clearly that the number of accidents involving vulnerable subjects decreases during the first months of the year to increase again in the first months of summer. Another decrease happens after July only for the number of accidents to start rising again from September until the end of the year when it reaches its peak.

Figure 44. Number of accidents throughout the year (per month)

Additionally, the trend was analyzed per day of the week (Figure 45), looking for patterns of increased risk. The data shows that accidents are more frequent on Fridays while Weekend days

are the ones with a lower frequency of accidents. This evidence might indicate that during work days accidents are more frequent.

Figure 45. Number of accidents throughout the week (per day)

To provide further details accidents' frequency was analyzed by hour of the day (Figure 46). The data shows that the first hours of the day have a very low frequency of accidents while from 7 to 17 the frequency is higher and fairly consistent. It also shows that at 18 there is the highest occurrence of accidents, this might be due to standard office hours (9-18).

Number of accidents by time of the day

Figure 46. Number of accidents throughout the day (per hour)

Lastly, weather conditions were also analyzed (Figure 47). The data shows that 74% of the accidents took place during sunny days while only 12,8% of accidents took place during a rainy day, the rest of the accidents took place mainly during cloudy days. Given this information it looks like adverse weather conditions are not the cause of higher risk of accidents for vulnerable subjects.

Number of accidents dependent on weather conditions

Figure 47. Number of accidents by weather condition

Additional analysis will be carried out when new datasets (GIS Data, AMT stops) will be received.

5 Conclusion and Future Works

This deliverable analytically describes the work done on the various Pilots use cases for the data available so far. The deliverable includes a detailed description of the modules from which the task is composed, which are the AI Pipelines developed and the Explainability module. The goal of this document is to present the extensive and thorough work done on the interpretation of the use cases and datasets to actual AI models and analytics insights. Furthermore, the presentation of the Explainable AI tools and algorithms selected will help to have the predictions of the models explained so the user will be able to understand why the models has made the prediction it did.

For future work and the next version of the deliverable there will be available more AI pipelines based on datasets for the new user stories which will be provided from all the pilots. Additional, APIs for all the Pipelines and the explainable tools will be constructed which will then be integrated to the VPME platform ready to be used by the user (Data Scientist / Policy Maker).

6 References

- [1] Gunning D, Aha D. DARPA's explainable artificial intelligence (XAI) program. *AI Mag* 2019;40(2):44–58. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1609/aimag.v40i2.2850>.
- [2] Guidotti, Riccardo and Monreale, Anna and Ruggieri, Salvatore and Turini, Franco and Giannotti, Fosca and Pedreschi, Dino. A Survey of Methods for Explaining Black Box Models, *ACM Computing Surveys*. Vol. 51, n 5.
- [3] Dwivedi, Rudresh and Dave, Devam and Naik, Het and Singhal, Smiti and Rana, Omer and Patel, Pankesh and Qian, Bin and Wen, Zhenyu and Shah, Tejal and Morgan, Graham and Ranjan, Rajiv. {Explainable AI (XAI): Core Ideas, Techniques and Solutions, 2022, *ACM Computing Surveys*, inpress.
- [4] Ajay Thampi. 2020. *Interpretable AI, Building explainable machine learning systems*. Manning Publications, USA
- [5] [Marco Túlio Ribeiro, Sameer Singh, Carlos Guestrí. Why Should {I} Trust You?: Explaining the Predictions of Any Classifier}. *Proceedings of the 22nd {ACM} {SIGKDD} International Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining*, 2016
- [6] Scott M Lundberg and Su-In Lee. 2017. A unified approach to interpreting model predictions. In *Advances in neural information processing systems*. 4765–4774.
- [7] Przemyslaw Biecek and Tomasz Burzykowski. *Explanatory Model Analysis*, Chapman and Hall, 2021, isbn 9780367135591, <https://pbiecek.github.io/ema/>
- [8] Przemyslaw Biecek. DALEX: Explainers for Complex Predictive Models in R. *Journal of Machine Learning Research*, 2018, vol. 19, pp 1-5, no84
- [9] *Deep Learning* (Ian J. Goodfellow, Yoshua Bengio and Aaron Courville), MIT Press, 2016.
- [10] Wei Di, Anurag Bhardwaj, and Jianing Wei. 2018. *Deep Learning Essentials: Your hands-on guide to the fundamentals of deep learning and neural network modeling*. Packt Publishing.
- [11] Michael A. Nielsen, "Neural Networks and Deep Learning", Determination Press, 2015.
- [12] Christopher M. Bishop. 2006. *Pattern Recognition and Machine Learning (Information Science and Statistics)*. Springer-Verlag, Berlin, Heidelberg.
- [13] Hunter, J. (2007). Matplotlib: A 2D graphics environment. *Computing in Science & Engineering*, 9(3), 90–95.
- [14] Xu, Feiyu & Uszkoreit, Hans & Du, Yangzhou & Fan, Wei & Zhao, Dongyan & Zhu, Jun. (2019). Explainable AI: A Brief Survey on History, Research Areas, Approaches and Challenges. 10.1007/978-3-030-32236-6_51.
- [15] Michael L. Waskom (2021). seaborn: statistical data visualization. *Journal of Open Source Software*, 6(60), 3021.
- [16] Plotly Technologies Inc. Collaborative data science. Montréal, QC, 2015. <https://plot.ly>.
- [17] Martín Abadi, Ashish Agarwal, Paul Barham, Eugene Brevdo, Zhifeng Chen, Craig Citro, Greg S. Corrado, Andy Davis, Jeffrey Dean, Matthieu Devin, Sanjay Ghemawat, Ian Goodfellow, Andrew Harp, Geoffrey Irving, Michael Isard, Rafal Jozefowicz, Yangqing Jia, Lukasz Kaiser, Manjunath

Kudlur, Josh Levenberg, Dan Mané, Mike Schuster, Rajat Monga, Sherry Moore, Derek Murray, Chris Olah, Jonathon Shlens, Benoit Steiner, Ilya Sutskever, Kunal Talwar, Paul Tucker, Vincent Vanhoucke, Vijay Vasudevan, Fernanda Viégas, Oriol Vinyals, Pete Warden, Martin Wattenberg, Martin Wicke, Yuan Yu, and Xiaoqiang Zheng. TensorFlow: Large-scale machine learning on heterogeneous systems, 2015. Software available from tensorflow.org.

[18] <https://modeloriented.github.io/ingredients/reference/index.html>

[19] https://modeloriented.github.io/iBreakDown/articles/vignette_iBreakDown_description.html

[20] <https://github.com/ModelOriented/auditor>